

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

Democracia em perigo: das notícias falsas ao abuso de poder político

 Reginaldo Gonçalves Gomes¹

Faculdade de Filosofia e Teologia (FAJE) e Universidade Federal de Ouro Preto (UFOP), Belo Horizonte, Minas Gerais, Brasil

Abstract

This article aims to demonstrate the need to strengthen democratic institutions and empower citizens to prevent the far right from co-opting and destabilizing society, bringing about social chaos and promoting conformity to the actions and ideas of a single leader. The hypothetical-deductive method is used in this research. The following themes are addressed: democracy, politics, electoral justice, electronic voting, the role of the far right, and digital militias. Possible conclusions include: Maintaining democracy in Brazil requires a strong and efficient electoral justice system to prevent candidates from leveraging political power to secure re-election or appoint their successors. The State must rigorously combat digital militias and enact specific laws to criminalize their activities, as well as individual actions that use social media to spread terror in society. There must be greater regulation of social media to prevent its misuse in committing crimes against individuals, vulnerable people, and minority groups in society.

Keywords: democracy; far-right; extremist groups; digital militias

Resumo

Este artigo tem como objetivo demonstrar a necessidade de fortalecer as instituições democráticas e capacitar os cidadãos para impedir que a extrema direita coopte e desestabilize a sociedade, trazendo o caos social e evitando a conformidade às ações e ideias de um líder. O método hipotético-dedutivo é utilizado nesta pesquisa. Os seguintes temas são abordados: democracia, política, justiça eleitoral, voto eletrônico, o papel da extrema direita e milícias digitais. Possíveis conclusões são: A manutenção da democracia no Brasil requer um sistema de justiça eleitoral forte e ágil para impedir que candidatos usem o poder político para se reelegerem ou elegerem seus sucessores escolhidos. O Estado deve combater rigorosamente as milícias digitais e promulgar leis específicas para criminalizar suas atividades, bem como ações individuais que usem as mídias sociais para espalhar terror na sociedade. Deve haver um maior controle sobre as mídias sociais para evitar seu uso indevido para crimes contra indivíduos, pessoas vulneráveis e minorias na sociedade.

Palavras-chave: democracia; extrema direita; grupos extremistas; milícias digitais

Recebido: 27 mar. 2024
Aprovado: 12 jun. 2025
Editor Chefe: Prof. Dr. José Fernando Vidal de Souza
Processo de Avaliação: *Double Blind Review*

Notas do autor

Conflito de interesses: O autor não declarou quaisquer conflitos de interesses potenciais.

Autor correspondente: Reginaldo Gonçalves Gomes - regisgomes17081964@gmail.com

Para citar este artigo

ABNT NBR 6023:2025

GOMES, Reginaldo Gonçalves. Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power. *Prisma Jurídico*, São Paulo, v. 24, e26344, p. 01-22, 2025. DOI <http://doi.org/10.5585/2025.26344>. Disponível em: <https://periodicos.uninove.br/prisma/article/view/26344>

¹ Doutor em Direito Processual pela Pontifícia Universidade Católica de Minas Gerais. <http://lattes.cnpq.br/7971186240841660>

Introduction

This article aims to investigate the relationship between extremism, abuse of political power, and democracy.

The abuse of political power in elections has always been a concern for society, the Executive, the Legislature, and the Judiciary, as this kind of abuse taints the free will of the voter.

The Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil, Article 14, §9, establishes the normality and legitimacy of elections as founding principles of the electoral process, safeguarding them “against the influence of economic power or the abuse of the exercise of function, position, or employment in direct or indirect administration.” In turn, the legislator created Complementary Law No. 64/90, which establishes judicial investigations in elections to curb the abuse of authority and political power, a common practice in Brazil.

Over the years, the jurisprudence of the Superior Electoral Court has consistently affirmed that the abuse of political power is detrimental to society, primarily because it can unduly influence the election of unscrupulous candidates.

It is worth recalling Norberto Bobbio’s observation that fundamental rights are constantly evolving (Bobbio, 1992, p. 18-19). In this context, contemporary societies place great value on the right to free and untainted suffrage.

Therefore, the State must intervene, as the legal and political systems must understand each other and, above all, work for the community's benefit, improving the means of presenting political ideas to voters to convince them of the best candidate rather than buying them (Tomaz, 2011, p. 66).

Society expects that its fundamental rights, inscribed in the Federal Constitution, especially regarding universal suffrage, will be respected, and that electoral campaigns will be clean, immaculate, without “slush funds,” illicit vote-buying. These are legitimate expectations that the Social State must adhere to.

Moreover, the State and society must be vigilant of the various ways in which the far right uses to destroy, undermine democracy, using social networks such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Telegram, WhatsApp etc., to spread hate speech and fake news, destabilize institutions, and create mass hysteria to sow chaos.

The theoretical framework adopted is Claude Lefort’s assertion that democracy is characterized by a separation between the symbolic and the real, and that, in this regime, power does not belong to the ruler, as it occupies an empty place (Lefort, 2014).

Thus, it is argued that the exercise of power without effective control and oversight succumbs to far-right extremist groups, allowing them to commit crimes and abuse political power while in government. The problem to be addressed is how the far right in Brazil acted on social media to practice abuse of political power to establish a dictatorial regime in Brazil.

The hypothesis is that the far right's use of social media enabled the spread of fake news and hate speech, instilling fear and terror among citizens by claiming that the left would turn the country into a communist and lawless state. Therefore, the intertwining of technology, extremism, and abuse of economic power will be analyzed. This article aims to demonstrate the necessity of strengthening democratic institutions, particularly the Federal Electoral Court, to prevent the far right from co-opting and dismantling them and from inciting social chaos.

The hypothetical-deductive method will be adopted, following Lakatos (2000, p. 71). This method begins by identifying a shortcoming in the body of knowledge from which a hypothesis is then formulated. Through deductive inference, the hypothesis is then tested by examining the predicted phenomena it encompasses. The objective of this study is to provide a political-legal analysis. Following the methodological guidance of Gustin and Fonseca Dias (2013), the research will be theoretical, employing techniques such as direct documentation and bibliographic analysis. This research will have an interdisciplinary character, as it will examine content from the political, legal, and philosophical domains to understand the phenomenon of abuse of political power and the use of social media by the far right in Brazil.

1 Democracy and Politics

The relationship between philosophy and politics is often perceived as one of mutual opposition. While the philosopher's task is to contemplate enduring and significant abstract and conceptual problems, the politician's role is to engage the public in transient issues of interest. However, there is a paradox in the relationship between philosophy and politics: although they often stand in opposition, they also sustain a reciprocal connection.

Claude Lefort (1991) asserts that the political sphere shapes society, molding social relations and staging them. He states that every society has its origin outside of itself and that "it opens itself from an opening that was not created by itself." For example, in pre-modern European times, it was understood that the immanent and transcendent body of the king, with its human and divine nature, served as a symbolic locus. The king's body incorporated society,

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

symbolizing the forms of social relations and conveying the idea of a link between the human and the divine.

In this context, when the idea that power is embodied in the person of the king, the prince, is destroyed, according to Lefort (1991), there is a democratic revolution, a “mutation” that disincorporates society, dislodges it from its foundation in divine will, and inaugurates a political modernity. Thus, modern regimes are characterized by the erosion of traditional certainties and the undermining of established sources of power. These regimes differ from each other in their relationship with the symbolic locus from which power originates.

A modern democratic regime keeps the place of power empty. Therefore, detached from the body of the king/ruler, society can no longer be embodied in a single body or linked to another transcendent. Society remains plural and indeterminate. And, according to Lefort (1991), despite the principle of popular sovereignty, the people do not occupy this symbolic place of power due to their ontological division and also due to the procedural constraints of democratic institutions.

Therefore, the empty space of power cannot even be occupied by a unity in democracy. Moreover, if this void of power is occupied by an “empirical figure,” there will not be a democracy, but rather an authoritarian society. Democracy, by nature, embraces conflict, whereas authoritarian regimes suppress and eliminate it. In a democratic society, conflict is institutionalized. In a democracy, rulers cannot have appropriate power or incorporate themselves into it. The exercise of power must be alternated periodically, as it should not be incorporated into the person of the ruler. Totalitarianism, in a certain way, has a link with democracy. It is the antithesis of democracy. It treats society and the State without any difference.

According to Lefort (1991), democracy is constantly threatened by totalitarianism because it can survive and take shape due to the indeterminacy of modernity. That is, “totalitarian tendencies arise with an attempt to close the experience of indeterminacy of political modernity.” Totalitarianism inverts the very ideas that come from the democratic revolution, which are the basis for the self-representation of democratic societies. Therefore, Lefort (1991) asserts that democracy is always at risk of succumbing to totalitarianism. To avoid totalitarianism, Lefort argues that we must interpret our society “in political terms,” that is, always keeping in mind the symbolism of collective power and that the place of power must always be empty to preserve the people’s freedom.

However, in practice, rulers do not conceive of power as an empty locus but rather equate it with themselves, rendering their rule totalitarian. In their eagerness to perpetuate their

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

authority, they resort to violence to suppress dissenting ideas and conflicts. There is no conflict in totalitarianism; it is stifled, silenced, and hidden away from the public sphere. People are arrested, tortured, and vilified to weaken their “soul” because the body can no longer withstand the hardships of violence.

Vigilance over the democratic regime must be continuous because the authoritarian ruler slowly destroys democratic institutions when they cannot do it in a single “blow.”

2 Abuse of Political Power in Brazil

Abuse of authority and political power by public officials during elections has been a concern of society, the legislature, and the judiciary, as this type of abuse taints the free will of the voter.

The Federal Constitution of Brazil, Article 14, §9, establishes the principles of regularity and legitimacy of elections as foundational principles of the electoral process, to be safeguarded “against the influence of economic power or the abuse of the exercise of function, position, or employment in the direct or indirect administration.” (emphasis added).

In 1990, the legislature enacted Supplementary Law No. 64/1990, which established the electoral judicial inquiry suit to revoke the mandate of any public official – mayor, governor, or president – who abuses authority and political power to secure votes in elections.

Thus, only a candidate who holds a political position, that is, is a public agent, and is running for reelection, can commit abuse of authority/political power, since Article 22 of Supplementary Law No. 64/90 establishes that abuse of authority is illegal.

According to José Jairo Gomes, “abuse of political power can be considered a form of abuse of authority, as it occurs in the public-state sphere and is practiced by public authorities” (Gomes, 2022, p. 767).

Similarly, Rodrigo Lopez Zilio (2018, p. 645, free translation) clarifies that

Abuse of authority occurs when an individual holding public office, employment, or function acts beyond the legal limits or the scope of their authorized powers. Such abuse presupposes the exercise of public power and, consequently, cannot apply to actions taken by persons not affiliated with the public administration (in the broad sense). (Free translation from the Portuguese language).

Regarding the abuse of political power, according to the jurisprudence of the Superior Electoral Court, it occurs “when the public agent, taking advantage of their functional position

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

and in a manifest deviation of purpose, compromises the equality of the contest and the legitimacy of the electoral process to benefit their candidacy or that of others” (RESPE No. 40898, Rapporteur Minister Edson Fachin, DJE 06/08/2019). The Superior Electoral Court defines abuse of political power as follows:

[...] 10. According to the case law of this Superior Electoral Court, the abuse of political power or authority, as outlined in Article 22, caput, of Complementary Law No. 64/90, is characterized when a public agent, taking advantage of their official position and manifestly deviating from the intended purpose, undermines the equality and legitimacy of the electoral contest to benefit their candidacy or that of third parties (RO no 172365/DF, Rapporteur: Justice Admar Gonzaga, DJe of 2/27/2018; RO no 466997/PR, Rapporteur: Justice Gilmar Mendes, DJe of 10/3/2016; REspe no 33230/RJ, Rapporteur: Justice João Otávio de Noronha, DJe 3/31/2016). [...] (TSE – REspe no 40898/SC – DJe, vol. 150, 8/6/2019, pp. 71–72). (Free translation from the Portuguese language).

It must be determined whether the acts were carried out by a public agent, in the use of their functional position, through a deviation of purpose and revealing an excess of patrimonial resources to the extent that it compromises the legitimacy of the electoral process to benefit a candidacy. If the answer is positive, there will be the practice of abusing political power. Thus, to characterize an act as political power abuse, it must be proven that it was performed by an individual holding public office.

According to §1 of Article 73 of Law No. 9.504/1997, a public official is any person who holds, even temporarily or without remuneration, by election or any other form of investiture or bond, a mandate or position within the organs or entities of the direct public administration.

The candidate who already holds a political position such as Mayor, Governor, President, and/or parliamentarian must be understood as an authority. Thus, only these authorities can commit the offense provided for in Article 22 of Complementary Law no. 64/90.

Another example of abuse of authority and/or political power was the declaration of ineligibility, for 8 years, against the former President of Brazil, Jair Messias Bolsonaro, due to the use of the position of President of the Republic.

In the judgment of the Judicial Action of Electoral Investigation N. 0600814-85.2022.6.00.0000, the Superior Electoral Court, by majority, declared the ineligibility of the former President of the Republic under the grounds that the former President met with “ambassadors of foreign countries on 07/18/2022 to attack the integrity of the electoral process, especially disseminating “informational disorder” regarding the electronic voting system” and also spread fake news about the electoral process, propagating misinformation about the

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

reliability of electronic voting machines. All of this is utilizing public goods and services, as well as media coverage.

Certainly, defining abuse of power is not an easy task, let alone impossible, to determine what constitutes abuse of power and what does not. It is certain that whenever the candidate or public agent deviates from the public purpose to unbalance the electoral campaign in their favor, they may be facing abuse of authority/political power, as provided for in Complementary Law n. 64/90.

Undoubtedly, the significant contribution of the rulings rendered by the Electoral Justice has been the strengthening of democracy. These rulings have been effective in safeguarding voting freedom. In short, it can be said that the contribution of the Electoral Justice to democracy has been immense.

The rulings of Brazil's Federal Electoral Justice – including electoral judges, Regional Electoral Courts, and the Superior Electoral Court – in defining what constitutes abuse of authority or political power have provided clear guidelines for candidates, ensuring they avoid such practices during their electoral campaigns.

3 The Denialist and Conspiratorial Rhetoric Driving Resistance to the Recognition of Election Results

The Federal Electoral Court is an institution vested with the competence and legitimacy to oversee elections under the 1988 Federal Constitution. Therefore, suits against the results of electronic voting machines must observe the due process established in the Electoral Legislation.

Supervision by authorized entities can occur at two moments: before sealing the electronic voting machines and during the voting process by the electors, according to Resolution No. 23.673, dated December 14, 2021, and Resolution No. 23.669, dated December 14, 2021.

The entities authorized to supervise the electronic voting machines in 2022, as per Article 6 of Resolution No. 23.673/2019, were:

I) Political parties, federations, and coalitions; II) Brazilian Bar Association; III) Public Prosecutor's Office; IV) National Congress; V) Supreme Federal Court; VI) Comptroller General of the Union; VII) Federal Police; VIII) Brazilian Computer Society; IX) Federal Council of Engineering and Agronomy; X) National Council of Justice; XI) National Council

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

of the Public Ministry; XII) Federal Court of Audit; XIII) Armed Forces; XIV) National Confederation of Industry, other members of the Industry System, and corporate entities belonging to the “S” System; XV) Brazilian private non-profit entities, with notorious activity in public management oversight and transparency, accredited with Superior Electoral Court; and XVI) Information technology departments of universities accredited with Superior Electoral Court.

These entities are granted authority under Resolution No. 23.673/2021/TSE to raise concerns regarding any technical issues in electronic voting machines before sealing. It is important that none of these entities, including the Armed Forces, reported any instance of fraud, error, or malfunction in the electronic voting machines in their official reports.

On the contrary, entities such as the Brazilian Bar Association and the Federal Court of Audit affirmed the integrity, transparency, and security of the electronic voting process. Similarly, under the provisions of Resolution No. 23.669/2021/TSE, which governs legal challenges related to the voting process, none of the supervising entities present during the election filed any legal action based on alleged facts suggesting fraud or irregularities in the electronic voting machines.

These entities are protected by Resolution No. 23.673/2021/TSE, under which they can question any technical problems existing in the electronic voting machines before they are sealed. It is worth noting that none of these entities, including the Armed Forces, reported any fraud, error, or malfunction in the electronic voting machines in their reports.

The opposite occurred. Entities such as the Brazilian Bar Association or the Federal Court of Audit confirmed the integrity, transparency, and security of the vote through electronic voting machines. Likewise, protected by Resolution No. 23.669/2021/TSE, which deals with suits to the voting process, the supervising entities during the voting did not file a lawsuit due to any “fact” that could highlight any indication of fraud in the electronic voting machines.

So, why was there fake news about fraud created around the electronic voting machines? Certainly, the arguments of fraud in the electronic voting machines are a construction to undermine the voting through electronic machines and the Electoral Court, because the far right in Brazil does not accept any result other than the election of its candidate.

The issue is neither legal nor technical, as stated before, the Brazilian legal system has made available to a large number of entities the right to participate in and supervise the electoral process, including electronic voting machines. Likewise, from a technical standpoint, the voting machines do not have flaws that compromise the voting process, as they are completely secure

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

against hacker attacks, being disconnected from the internet, and featuring an impenetrable internal (sealed) system at present.

Therefore, the issue is political, and the law can only mitigate it, as only with education and research will citizens learn to build a lasting democracy.

The denial of the legitimacy of the Electoral Court and electronic voting had already begun in 2018, with far-right extremist groups, businessmen, and those who support and follow them claiming that the voting machines were fraudulent. However, it is reasonable to assume that the candidates themselves did not genuinely believe there was fraud in the voting machines, given that they had been elected to multiple terms as Federal Deputies.

This discourse against the use of electronic voting machines is a strategy to dismantle institutions. This strategy is part of the extreme right worldwide. It did not originate in Brazil; rather, many individuals in the country amplify the voice of an extreme far-right movement driven by political and economic power, as well as by conservative and radical religious groups seeking to advance their political agenda of dismantling institutions as a means of controlling the state. Therefore, there are powerful business interests and political actors who possess the economic and political influence to destabilize Brazil's political and judicial systems.

The far right seeks to create chaos as a means of consolidating power. In Brazil, between 2018 and 2022, this strategy became evident through the systematic weakening of the Ministry of the Environment, environmental agencies, and popular participation councils. Additionally, a militarized policy was implemented to arm supporters in preparation for a potential uprising against democratic institutions, if deemed necessary.

In Brazil, there is a wave of far-right violence that began in 2013, culminating in the impeachment of President Dilma Rousseff and continuing in 2018. This violence was fostered as a state policy to maintain power: It would be naive to assume that the far-right movement originated in Brazil and operates solely within its borders.

In this context of political system destabilization, the Public Prosecutors' Office, the Police, and the Judiciary can be co-opted to play a predominant role in contributing to the dismantling of the political system when they engage in "operations" that have the pretext of eradicating corruption in the political realm but, in fact, only contribute to the destabilization of politics and instill an anti-political sentiment in the people. A false sense of security is fostered, suggesting that these agencies are combating political corruption, while in reality, they are targeting specific political parties and instilling fear among the population.

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

David Broder (2020) states that the far-right in Italy “began 30 years ago and that the Operation Clean Hands, an investigation initiated in 1992 in Italy against corruption among public agents and businessmen, served to collapse the 'Christian Democracy' Party and the 'Italian Socialist Party, which were two mass parties.” This created an opening for the far right to seize control of the political landscape with popular support.

Likewise, the same phenomenon occurred in the United States with the election of Donald Trump and a radical far-right discourse, as well as allegations of voting fraud in the United States. Similarly, Brexit in England, fueled by the far-right, was a way for England to isolate itself from the rest of Europe, as it did not agree with the immigration and economic policies adopted by most European Union members. Brexit was driven by the idea of an England solely for the English, like Donald Trump, former President of the United States, advocated for an America exclusively for Americans.

It is also important not to forget that Fujimori, former President of Peru, between 1990 and 2000, attacked judges by calling them “scoundrels,” referred to the political elite as corrupt, and weakened democratic institutions. Finally, on April 5, 1992, Fujimori dissolved the Congress and the constitution (Levitsky; Ziblat, 2018, pp. 78-79). Therefore, democratic institutions were so fragile that they were unable to respond effectively to Fujimori’s coup. Unsurprisingly, Fujimori relied on the broad base of voters who supported him, manipulating them through lies and disinformation.

In Brazil, a similar investigation to the “Operation Clean Hands” was created, known as “Operation Car Wash,” to combat corruption among political agents and businessmen. However, the investigation known as 'Operation Car Wash' focused exclusively on politicians affiliated with the Workers' Party, leading to the perception that it was orchestrated by individuals with economic and political power to prevent the prominent political leader Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva from participating in the 2018 elections. Lula enjoys strong popular support, as evidenced by his victory in the 2022 elections.

Within the scope of “Operation Car Wash,” former President Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva was convicted in several corruption cases. However, the Supreme Federal Court, in the judgment of various appeals filed by former President Lula, overturned all convictions imposed by the Federal Judge of the Federal Justice of Curitiba, confirmed by the Regional Federal Court of the 4th Region (Paraná, Santa Catarina, and Rio Grande do Sul), based in Porto Alegre, Rio Grande do Sul.

4 The use of Technology by the Far Right

The use of technology by the far right in Brazil is a phenomenon that deserves a critical and attentive analysis. Just like in other countries, Brazil has witnessed a concerning rise in the dissemination of extremist ideologies through digital platforms. This scenario is characterized by a series of challenges that impact social cohesion, democracy, and the pursuit of a fair and equitable society.

The far right worldwide has found in social media platforms such as “Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, and WhatsApp,” along with other technological tools, an effective and globally-reaching means to spread its ideas, disseminate distorted information, and establish connections with its followers. Employing an aggressive and polarizing approach, these groups have utilized tactics of disinformation and emotional manipulation to garner support and build a base of loyal followers.

They propagate false narratives and conspiracy theories that amplify fear and anger among their followers, widening rifts between people and eroding trust in democratic institutions. According to David Nemer (2022, p. 160),

[...] These radical groups, too, have made their voices heard outside of WhatsApp. They have driven protests that called on Bolsonaro to shutter the Brazilian Congress, shut down the country’s judiciary, and even return to military rule. Such ideas show how radical Brazilian discourse has become under a president who has long celebrated the country’s deadly and oppressive military dictatorship.

These tactics were employed in the United States by former President Donald Trump and his supporters, as well as in Brazil by many far-right extremist groups and their allies. The creation of ideological bubbles and the dissemination of fake news have been common strategies to expand the reach of extremist narratives. Recommendation algorithms present on social media platforms have contributed to individuals being exposed only to content that reinforces their pre-existing beliefs, creating an environment of constant reaffirmation of radical views and the isolation of divergent perspectives.

This spread of false information also has a significant impact on public discourse and the political process. Disinformation can distort perceptions of crucial issues, undermine trust in institutions and elections, and hinder society's ability to make informed decisions.

Employing these strategies, the far-right extremist groups created an atmosphere of conflict in Brazil by attempting to destabilize institutions, especially the Supreme Federal Court, and attacking any citizen who opposed their aspirations with false news.

Rocha (2023) provides the following analysis of the actions of “Bolsonarism:”

In 2018, Bolsonaroism made unrestrained use of the “inductions dangerous, drunken prophecies, libels and Dreams,” taking to the letter the lesson of Richard III, and with the same objective, namely, “to set [...] deadly hate”—in this case, between Brazilian society and anything that evoked the monstrous phantom of communism, of the left, in short of petismo. Cultural war only triumphs when it personalizes the causes of historical processes, that is, when it embodies the false moralism of the customs agenda in individuals who begin to channel the violence generated by ideological radicalization, becoming targets of persecution marked by hatred and even by the desire for the physical elimination of the other. (Free translation from the Portuguese language).

The dissemination of hate speech and racial, ethnic, gender, and other forms of discrimination was extensively used by Bolsonaroist groups. Through technology, messages laden with prejudices are spread, fueling conflicts and undermining peaceful coexistence among the various groups in Brazilian society. Similarly, the strategic use of social media and messaging platforms has also been employed to organize protests, demonstrations, and political mobilizations. Undoubtedly, freedom of expression is a fundamental pillar of democracy.

However, it is important to distinguish between the legitimate right to protest and express opinions and the incitement of violence or speech aimed at undermining democratic institutions. What is observed in the actions of the far right is the continuous practice of hate crimes, attacking honor and human dignity. The far-right criminally exploited social media platforms to spread distorted realities and discriminatory, racist, and misogynistic ideologies.

Max Fischer (2022) tells the story of Brazilian psychologist Tatiana Lionço, who gave a short lecture on combating homophobia in schools. Afterwards, her words were distorted by the far-right, who posted an edited version of the lecture on YouTube, destroying Tatiana Lionço’s life. As cited:

IT HAD BEEN seven years, Tatiana Lionço recalled, her voice straining, since a viral YouTube video had destroyed her life. In 2012, Lionço, a psychologist, had spoken on a panel about combating homophobia in schools. She told the tiny audience of academics and policymakers that parents should be reassured that there was nothing unusual in young children expressing curiosity about one another’s bodies or clothes.

Soon after, a far-right lawmaker edited footage of the event, rearranging her words to make it appear that she had encouraged homosexuality and sex between children. The lawmaker, widely considered a fringe oddity, had few political allies and little direct power. But he had a substantial following on YouTube, where he posted the edited footage. Far-right YouTubers, then a small but active community, reposted the misleading video, adding their own misinformation-filled commentary. Lionço represented a global communist-homosexual conspiracy, they said. She had endorsed pedophilia. She was distributing “gay kits” for schools to use to convert children to homosexuality. Their claims spread to Twitter and Facebook. Comments on the videos filled with calls for her to be killed. Lionço’s friends and colleagues initially dismissed it as social media noise. Until the manufactured story became consensus reality on the platforms, outraging ordinary citizens. Many called her university demanding she be fired. They accused her employer, and anyone who supported her, of endangering children. Her friends and colleagues distanced themselves. “I was left all alone with this,” Lionço told me. She paused, her face tightening, and looked down at her lap. Maybe people in her life felt ashamed that they’d allowed this to happen, she said. “I think people are afraid it might happen to them.” Even after she had mostly retreated from public life, the far-right YouTubers, whose audiences were exploding in size, kept pushing the story of the academic communist plotting to sexualize children. Though she eventually returned to teaching, her life has never been the same, stalked by infamy wherever she goes. Death threats remain a constant presence, as do whispers of suspicion even from like-minded peers. “I am exhausted. It’s been seven years,” she said, covering her face with her hands. “It broke me. This is the worst part for me. I feel alone.”

Lionço is Brazilian. In the fall of 2018, the fringe lawmaker and YouTuber who’d launched the disinformation campaign against Lionço six years earlier, a man named Jair Bolsonaro, ran to become her country’s president. Everyone had expected him to lose. Instead he won in a 10-point landslide. It was the most significant event in global politics since the election of Donald Trump. The world’s sixth-largest country came under the command of a far-right conspiracist. He oversaw the destruction of millions of acres of Amazon rain forest, signaled support for far-right violence, relentlessly attacked Brazil’s democratic institutions, and gutted its bureaucracies (FISCHER, 2022).

Pages, groups, and personal profiles have been created to share news, videos, memes, and speeches aligned with this ideology. These pages and groups often gained many followers and likes, expanding the reach of their messages.

Far-right extremist groups have been using platforms such as X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, Telegram, YouTube, and WhatsApp to spread their opinions directly and quickly. Specific hashtags were used to generate trends and attract the attention of the media and the public.

An instant messaging application played a crucial role in spreading information among closed groups of far-right followers. Private messaging platforms played a significant role in facilitating the rapid dissemination of messages, fake news, and conspiracy theories, often reaching large audiences within a short period.

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

Even though these platforms had moderators tasked with blocking the spread of fake news and hate speech, it was not enough to stop extremist groups, who managed to bypass platform controls and spread discord across the world.

Some channels gained millions of views and subscribers, allowing their creators to reach a wide and engaged audience. Although with a greater focus on images and short videos, Instagram was also used to promote far-right content. Profiles of political figures and influencers were utilized to disseminate messages and engage followers.

Telegram was also employed by the far right to create private groups and channels for disseminating content. The platform's security and privacy features made it particularly appealing to these actors, enabling them to communicate more discreetly.

Rocha provides the following analysis of the use of social media by Bolsonaroist groups: "in the realm of social media, beyond avoiding information that produces dissonance, digital masses seek confirmation of their beliefs in the vast contemporary marketplace of alternative facts, fake news, and irrational theories – that is, YouTube" [...] (Rocha, 2021).

Through these social media platforms, the far-right extremist groups managed to create a powerful network for communication and content dissemination, reaching a wide audience and influencing public opinion on various political and social issues. The exploitation of these digital platforms played a significant role in the growth and strengthening of this ideology worldwide, highlighting that individuals who did not initially identify with far-right agendas began to support them.

Over the past years, several cases of fake news and misleading information spread by the far-right on social media have been identified globally. Some of these examples include conspiracy theories. The far-right often shared conspiracy theories about political opponents, institutions, and events, spreading unfounded narratives not based on facts.

Likewise, disinformation regarding social and environmental issues, which involves false news related to sensitive topics such as LGBT+ rights, social movements, and environmental concerns, has been used to generate polarization and fuel intolerance.

Moreover, the manipulation of information about political opponents, including the use of out-of-context quotes, doctored images, and distorted statements, has been commonly used to attack leaders who oppose the far-right.

Finally, there is the use of exaggerated facts. In some cases, real facts were exaggerated or interpreted in a biased manner to promote a specific narrative and favor the far-right agenda. In Brazil, a cultural war was triggered by far-right extremist groups, whose ideology has no

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

qualms about destroying everything and everyone in the name of a project to dominate institutions and Brazil for its followers, who lack critical thinking (Rocha, 2021).

These practices of spreading false and distorted information have been widely debated and concern society, as they undermine trust in the media and democratic institutions. The dissemination of fake news on social media is a complex issue that involves various actors, from individual users to social media platforms, and the role of media literacy in shaping critical and well-informed citizens.

Addressing the challenges posed by harmful uses of technology requires a multifaceted approach. Technology companies play a crucial role in promoting transparency and holding users accountable for their actions on the platforms. Additionally, fostering media literacy is essential for citizens to recognize and combat misinformation. Likewise, it is the responsibility of the government to implement appropriate regulation of social media and other digital platforms to prevent misuse and to ensure that individual freedoms are not invoked as a justification for actions that harm society.

Thus, the use of technology by the far-right in Brazil poses a complex and multifaceted challenge to society. A collective effort involving governments, companies, and civil society is necessary to address the negative impacts of this technological exploitation and to strive towards building a healthier, more inclusive, and respectful digital environment for all Brazilians. Only through such efforts can democratic dialogue be promoted and solutions be sought that consider the diversity and interests of the entire population.

5 Digital Militias

Digital militias in Brazil represent a growing threat to democracy, freedom of expression, and the quality of public discourse. Lobo; Bolzan de Moraes, and Nemer (2021, p. 359) provide the following definition of digital militias:

Objectively and succinctly, as a first conceptual approximation, digital militias—a term popularized by its widespread use after the 2018 elections in Brazil—can be understood as an association of individuals connected in a more or less flexible

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

manner and lacking any formal legal structure, who act in a coordinated or orchestrated way on the web, mostly through social media platforms, making use of bots, automated accounts, and fake profiles to conduct campaigns of attacks and/or cancellation targeting the image and reputation of occasional opponents, as well as spreading disinformation and discourse with markedly authoritarian, if not neofascist, content.

Within this conceptual framework, the existence of digital militias can be recognized; however, due to the opacity and illegality of their practices, their actual internal structure and organization remain unknown, which makes their identification and legal classification more difficult. (Free translation).

Therefore, digital militias are organized groups that operate on social media, intending to disseminate distorted information, fake news, hate speech, and attack political opponents. These coordinated actions aim to manipulate public opinion, construct narratives favorable to specific interests, and discredit critical voices, often through illicit means and criminal behavior to achieve their objectives.

Digital militias operate on various online platforms, including social media, messaging apps, forums, and other digital spaces. They utilize these platforms to disseminate information, promote their ideologies, and execute coordinated actions aimed at influencing public opinion and shaping political discourse.

The activities of digital militias are not limited to any specific geographical location and can be found operating globally, targeting different audiences and regions. Their impact can be significant, affecting the perception of social and political issues and contributing to the polarization of public discourse in various countries.

One of the defining characteristics of digital militias is their capacity to construct ideological echo chambers, wherein members are confined to virtual environments that continuously reinforce their preexisting beliefs and worldviews.

This segmentation, amplified by social media algorithms, hinders dialogue and the exchange of ideas among people with different perspectives, further polarizing society. These ideological bubbles are led by a leader who provides them with instructions on how to act. This leader is always a totalitarian, as they aspire to make society obedient to their views and actions.

The cohesion of the social group depends on the leader's "action and knowledge," as well explained by Claude Lefort (1986, p. 286) when discussing totalitarianism:

Totalitarianism presupposes the conception of a society which is sufficient unto itself and, since the society is signified in power, the conception of a power which is sufficient unto itself. In short, it is when the action and knowledge of the leader are measured only by the criterion of the organization, when the cohesion or integrity of

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

the social body turns out to depend exclusively on the action and knowledge of the leader, that we leave the traditional frameworks of absolutism, despotism, and tyranny. The process of identification between power and society, the process of homogenizing the social space, and the process of enclosing both society and power are linked together to constitute the totalitarian system. With the constitution of this system, the representation of a 'natural' order is reestablished, but this order is supposed to be social-rational and does not tolerate apparent divisions or hierarchies.

Social media platforms bear significant responsibility in the dissemination of hate speech by the far right, as their algorithms tend to amplify the relevance of such posts by delivering and promoting them to a much larger audience.

And according to Lobo, Bolzan de Moraes, and Nemer (2021, p. 355),

The danger posed by the misuse of new technologies to democracy lies precisely in the way they serve to weaken freedom and dialogue—the very conditions that allow for the formation of free thought and the consolidation of personal choices—while also becoming a vehicle for attacks on human rights, spreading hatred and prejudice (NOBLE, 2018). In other words, the connections between democracy and technology break down when technology and its use reduce or render unfeasible the democratic process as a contest based on rules accepted by all, and when they call into question elements inherent to democracy, such as fundamental rights and institutions. (Our free translation from the original in Brazilian Portuguese language). (Free translation from the Portuguese language).

These militias are not restricted to a single political spectrum but have been associated with different ideological currents in Brazil. Whether from the left or the right, these groups have been responsible for coordinated attacks against public figures, journalists, academics, and ordinary citizens who dare to express divergent opinions.

The spread of fake news is one of the weapons used by digital militias. By distorting information, they aim to influence public opinion and shape perceptions about specific issues or individuals. The impact of this type of misinformation can be devastating, eroding trust in democratic institutions, fueling hatred, and contributing to social fragmentation.

The far right also employs fake profiles and bots to increase the dissemination of content produced by digital militias. These automated accounts can amplify the visibility of certain messages, making them appear more popular and relevant than they are. This creates a false sense of consensus and influence, distorting the public perception of what constitutes a majority opinion.

These practices not only threaten the integrity of public discourse but can also jeopardize the safety and privacy of individuals targeted by these attacks. Moreover, the spread of hate

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

speech and threats against specific individuals or groups can lead to an atmosphere of violence and intolerance that undermines social cohesion and societal harmony.

There are numerous cases of threats carried out by the far right simply because they cannot tolerate differing ideas. One particular case involves human rights lawyer Debora Diniz, who faced multiple threats from the far right. The YouTube channel of Küster in Londrina, Paraná, Brazil, dedicated itself to attacking Debora Diniz by spreading false news that she forced abortions on women who did not wish to undergo the procedure (Fischer, 2022).

In Brazil, digital militias played a significant role in the 2018 elections by spreading fake news and distorting information to undermine opposing candidacies, including through the involvement of an advisor within the former presidential administration, which started in 2019. In the words of David Nemer (2022, p. 159-1690),

In their view, the only way to save Brazil was to do what Bolsonaro didn't: organize an armed insurgency to completely cleanse the legislative and judicial branches of government's past ills. These insurgents, almost all of whom once belonged to pro-Bolsonaro groups before the election, have ironically exposed some of the dirtiest practices that occurred on WhatsApp during the campaign. Many of them have alleged that they were compensated between US\$100 and US\$250 per week to distribute pro-Bolsonaro content. By revealing this, they implicitly criticized influential groups of businessmen who they said financed the network, and they suggested that virtual militias (known as the Virtual Activist Movement) were paid to infiltrate WhatsApp groups and spread misinformation. They haven't directly implicated Bolsonaro's campaign team; however, they have said that at least one person who is currently an adviser in Bolsonaro's government was among those paid to feed fake news to his supporters.

To combat digital militias, governments, technology companies, and civil society need to collaborate. Social media platforms must invest in tools for detecting and combating misinformation, making algorithms more transparent and accountable. Additionally, media and digital literacy education are crucial to empower citizens to recognize and report the spread of fake news and hate speech.

It is necessary to safeguard the integrity of the digital space, ensuring that social networks are safe and healthy environments for public discourse, the exchange of ideas, and the practice of democracy. The fight against digital militias is a battle that requires collective efforts to preserve the fundamental principles of freedom, justice, and equality in our society.

In the Brazilian legal context, certain laws criminalize the activities of digital militias. Article 288-A of the Brazilian Penal Code establishes that it is a crime to constitute, organize, join, maintain, or finance a paramilitary organization, private militia, group, or squad with the intent to commit any of the crimes defined in the Code.

Although this article was incorporated into the Penal Code by Law No. 12.720 of 2012, it may also be applied to cases involving digital militias, which fall under the category of 'private militias' as defined in Article 288-A.

Likewise, Law No. 12.850/2013 characterizes a criminal organization as an association of four or more individuals, structurally organized and characterized by the division of tasks, even if informal, aimed at obtaining, directly or indirectly, any advantage through the commission of criminal offenses punishable by a maximum sentence of more than four years or a transnational nature (Lobo, Bolzan de Moraes, and Nemer, 2021, p. 370).

Thus, digital militias comprised of four or more people with an organized structure and a common criminal objective qualify as criminal organizations under the Brazilian Penal Code.

In Brazilian Electoral Law, individuals who disseminate false information about a candidate during electoral propaganda may be subject to imprisonment for two to eight years, as established in Article 326-A, paragraph 3 of the Electoral Code, as cited below:

Article 326-A. To cause the initiation of a police investigation, judicial proceeding, administrative investigation, civil inquiry, or administrative misconduct action, falsely attributing to someone the commission of a crime or infraction while knowing the person to be innocent, for electoral purposes:
Penalty – imprisonment from two (2) to eight (8) years, and a fine.
§1º The penalty is increased by one-sixth if the perpetrator acts anonymously or under a false name.
§2º The penalty is reduced by half if the accusation concerns a misdemeanor.
§3º The same penalties shall apply to anyone who, being demonstrably aware of the accused's innocence and acting with electoral intent, disseminates or spreads, by any means or in any form, the act or fact falsely attributed to the individual. (Included by Law No. 13,834/2019). (Free translation from the Portuguese language).

Brazil already has a legal framework that could be applied to digital militias. However, specific legislation should be enacted to clearly define and punish crimes committed by these groups, eliminating any legal ambiguity.

6 Final Remarks

Preserving democracy in Brazil requires a robust and efficient electoral justice system to prevent political candidates from exploiting their political power to seek re-election or secure the election of their protegés.

Citizens must be empowered not to conform to the logic of a ruler or leader, but rather to engage politically and cultivate empathy. Totalitarianism arises when society surrenders to the despotic teachings of a leader and fails to think critically and broadly about social issues.

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

On the other hand, far-right extremist digital militias are totalitarian and pose a threat to democracy as they spread disinformation and manipulate public opinion. The far right's use of technology has exacerbated polarization, undermining social cohesion and hindering collective efforts to address the country's challenges.

Furthermore, electronic voting must be preserved, as it helps prevent electoral fraud and protects the voter's will from being distorted by those who attempt to influence the vote unlawfully. As Reginaldo Gonçalves Gomes states, 'electronic voting is an important tool in ensuring the transparency and security of the electoral process' (Gonçalves Gomes, 2021, p. 60).

The abuse of economic power, in turn, can distort the electoral process by giving candidates with greater financial resources disproportionate advantages over their competitors, thereby restricting the plurality of voices in the political arena.

Therefore, the electoral justice system must remain vigilant to these issues and act decisively and impartially to uphold the integrity of the electoral process and protect Brazilian democracy. At the same time, society must remain vigilant and actively engaged in combating digital militias, disinformation, and extremism, while promoting a healthy public debate grounded in facts.

Technology can be an ally in this process, provided it is used ethically and responsibly to promote transparency, citizen participation, and the pursuit of solutions that reflect the interests and needs of all segments of society. Only then can we build a more just, inclusive, and democratic political environment in Brazil.

The state must confront digital militias rigorously, promoting the creation of specific laws to criminalize their practices, as well as the criminalization of individual activities that use social media to spread terror in society. It is essential to implement more effective control of social media to prevent its use for crimes against vulnerable individuals and minorities in society.

The creation of specific criminal offenses to criminalize the illicit activities of digital militias and far-right extremist groups who use pseudo-journalism for criminal purposes is necessary because existing norms in the Penal Code and the Electoral Code are not sufficient to curb this new form of virtual crime.

Finally, it is also necessary to address the problem of extremism and fake news in education, through school programs focused on teaching subjects that explain what news, information, truth, falsehood, and science are as a way to teach our children the difference between living in a Democratic Rule of Law and living in a Republic of chaos, falsehoods,

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

racism, and discrimination based on gender, skin color, and class. Subjects such as philosophy, sociology, history, Portuguese language, biological sciences, mathematics, and physics, among others, should embed approaches aimed at rejecting denialism, fascism, and the lies spread to incite hatred and chaos in society.

References

BOBBIO, Norberto. **A era dos direitos**. Tradução de Carlos Nelson Coutinho. Rio de Janeiro: Campus, 1992.

BOBBIO, Norberto. **O futuro da democracia**. Uma defesa das regras do jogo. Tradução de Marco Aurélio Nogueira. 14ª ed. São Paulo: Paz e Terra, 2017.

BRASIL. **Código Eleitoral**. Lei nº 4.737, de 15 de julho de 1965, que institui o Código Eleitoral. [Http://www.planalto.gov.br](http://www.planalto.gov.br). Acesso em: 7, abr. 2025.

BRODER, David. **First, they took Rome**: How the populist right conquered Italy. London: Verso Books, 2020.

FISCHER, Max. **The chaos machine**: The inside story of how social media rewired our minds and our world. E-book. New York: Little, Brown and Company Hachette Book Group, 2022.

GOMES, José Jairo. **Direito Eleitoral**. 18ª ed. Barueri/São Paulo: Atlas, 2022.

GOMES, Reginaldo Gonçalves. **Tutela coletiva no Direito Eleitoral**: Legitimidade dos interessados difusos na fiscalização das eleições. Belo Horizonte: Editora Dialética, 2021.

GUSTIN, Miracy Barbosa de Souza; DIAS, Maria Tereza Fonseca. **(Re)Pensando a Pesquisa Jurídica**. 2.ed. Belo Horizonte: Dey Rey, 2013.

LAKATOS, Eva Maria; MARCONI, Moreira de Andrade. **Metodologia Científica**. São Paulo: Atlas, 2000, p. 71.

LEFORT, Claude. **Essais sur le politique**. XIX-XX Siècles. E-book. France: Éditeur Le Seuil, 2014.

LEFORT, Claude. **Pensando o político**: ensaios sobre democracia, revolução e liberdade. Tradução Eliana M. Souza. Rio de Janeiro: Paz e Terra, 1991.

LEFORT, Claude. **The political forms of modern society**. Edited and introduced by John B. Thompson. E-book. The Mit Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts, 1986.

LEVITSKY, Steven; Daniel Ziblatt. **Como as democracias morrem**. Tradução Renato Aguiar. 1º ed. Rio de Janeiro, Zahar, 2018.

Democracy in danger: from fake news to abuse of political power

LOBO, Edilene; Bolzan de Moraes, José Luís; Nemer, David. **Democracia em perigo:** compreendendo as ameaças das milícias digitais no Brasil. Revista Estudos eleitorais, Brasília, DF. V. 15, n. 2, p. 8-380, jul./dez. 2021.

NEMER, David. **Technology of the oppressed:** Inequity and the digital mundane in favelas of Brazil. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press, 2022.

ROCHA, João Cezar de Castro. **Bolsonarismo:** da guerra cultural ao terrorismo doméstico: retórica do ódio e dissonância cognitiva coletiva. 1ª ed. E-book. Belo Horizonte: Autêntica, 2023.

ROCHA, João Cezar de Castro. **Guerra cultural e retórica do ódio.** Crônicas de um Brasil pós-político. E-Book. Editora Caminhos: Goiânia, 2021.

TOMAZ, Carlos Alberto de Simões. **Constituição, política e a ordem internacional herárquica.** Uma reflexão a partir da visão pragmático-sistêmica de Luhmann. Editora CRV. Curitiba, 2011.

ZILIO, Rodrigo Lópes. **Direito Eleitoral.** 6ª ed. Porto Alegre: Verbo Jurídico, 2018.

